

Paper 2

**A STUDY ON ISSUES AND CHALLENGES FACED BY PRIMARY
TEACHER’S IN FRAMING THE CURRICULUM IN PRESENT
SCENARIO WITH REFERENCE TO SOUTH CANARA.**

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ABSTRACT

Curriculum modification emerged as an important focal point in streamlining the educational system and strong weightage was cited on its functioning. The educationists in schools were expected to play a critical role in its efficient implementation. Curriculum changes determine to gain both the teacher and the learner. Poor capacitation of teachers in productively implementing the curriculum and lack of needed resources are contributing factor that forces on proper and effective implementation of curriculum changes.

As a result this study investigated the issues and a challenge faced by the school stakeholders in South Canara which was generated through structured questionnaire and interaction with the school teacher’s opinion to reassess a rich description and justification. In the present scenario issues like poor academic presentation of the learners, curriculum innovations lack the sense of ownership from stakeholders, miscommunication of innovations and lack of regular monitoring and appraisal which has led to the issues and problems towards curriculum implementation.

Keywords: Curriculum, Questionnaire, Educational, Opinion, Problems.

Curriculum growth is a step-by-step progression which is used to create optimistic enhancements in the courses offered by a school or university. The changes in the world and the new findings have to be incorporated and roped into the education. A curriculum expansion is a continuous evolvement. It must have all the ingredients of planners have to explore thoroughly the nature and qualification for which it is planned. The essential principle of curriculum planning is either the students must fit to the curriculum or the curriculum must fit in for the students.

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Issues

- ✓ The teachers of the present days resist to accept new changes as it mean additional work and time investment. It consumes lot of time and even need lot of preparation and reference. A respectable curriculum is evolved out solid enthusiastic and constant work.
- ✓ The teachers are not trained to imbibe the new learning accomplishments and approaches. The teachers are to be mobilised and be convinced for a crucial role in stimulating improvement.
- ✓ Creativity development is quite essential for the overall development of human being, but it is elapsed that knowledge cannot be delivered, it has to be shaped. So we should stress on creativity
- ✓ Life skills and other skills are indispensable for personal growth as they facilitate to deal with life complications more complexities. These skills include problem solving, interpersonal relations,, effective communication, stress management. The main issue is that today’s education is memory based and no active involvement of students. So we are deficient in the growth of life skills which are indispensable for managing daily life.
- ✓ The values of young minds have been eroded. This is probably due to advancement of Science and technology. All kinds of information can be accessed. All the transactions would be online, so the young minds will be deviated and are prone to malpractices.

Challenges

- ✓ Corruption in one of the major contributors in eroding the quality of education. Huge donations to the management for seeking admission are increasing. In private schools the situation is still worse as teachers get full salary but part payment goes back to the management in the form of blank cheques.
- ✓ The education led technologies is being distorted. The Doctors, Government servants, lawyers, politicians the so called saviours off society are highly corrupt. Old age homes and suicides are increasing. Value education is not a part of the curriculum. If it is existing religion and hatred are spread through value education.
- ✓ There are lot of Curriculum issues that puzzle today’s generation who really aim to make a career in Engineering, Medical or Business Administration. It is an irony that there is no consistency in the curriculum for the same programme. Quite repeatedly the syllabus is revised without bearing in mind the existing requirement of an industry.
- ✓ Very few teachers are involved in curriculum designing. The teacher is not only a receiver of the curriculum, but also a modifier and transmitter. Also for her not to overturn from the objectives,

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goals and aims of the curriculum planned, she must be part of the curriculum scheduling and development progression.

Remedies

- ✓ Primary education is the strength of education in a country like India. If the teachers at this level lack skill, untrained and paid very less, all the future studies will be at stake. So more priority is required on primary education. The weaker and less reputed college end up with poor students. This affects their employability prospects.
- ✓ A teacher should both an entrepreneur and architect. They should not restrict to classroom only, but move into the technological world and keep in pace with the current trends. Income should never be criteria, but training should be regular and a necessity.
- ✓ Both the hardware and the software changes have to be incorporated. The hardware changes are new classrooms, books. Playground and equipments and the software is affect the content of curriculum.
- ✓ India needs to offer quality education to many without disparities. Admission should be strictly based on merit not religion or caste, even financial support should be rendered on merit. It should be affordable to all irrespective of social background. Groundless reservations divided the society and lead to brain drain.
- ✓ Our education system should reward people who deserve it. They should recognise the unique contributions. Creativity should be encouraged. Ranks should be awarded accordingly.

Objective of the study

- To evaluate the challenges faced by teachers in transaction of curriculum.
- To study the issues faced by the teachers in the transaction of curriculum and remedies for it.
- To provide suggestions for the improvement of the curriculum

Scope of the study

The scope of this study is confined to the teachers of South Canara. The study throws light of Primary teachers in the curriculum transaction. This study can help to find the perception of the teachers.

Methodology:

Teachers' working in primary education was the main source of primary data. It was collected from the teachers working in different schools through a well-structured questionnaire. The area of study is limited to the district of South Canara and the researcher has proposed the convenient sampling techniques for the

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selection of respondents. Finally 200 respondents were selected and included the study. The Secondary data is collected through Journals on the internet.

Research limitations

- The analysis is done based on both primary and secondary data available at various sources but specifically confined to a small region.
- Time was the crucial factor
- The responses may be quite casual. This may be due to lack of interest.
- The study has been taken from a small population may not be applicable to others

Review of literature

John Dewey in his writings has stressed the needs for experimental learning. He is of the opinion that curriculum development is frequently affected by educational theories from time to time further posing a challenge to the curriculum developers.

The procedure of curriculum development was influenced by other educational theorists like Ralph Tyler and Hilda Taba through rational models. These were consequently reconceptualised and expanded by curriculum developers such as Skilbeck (1984) and Print (1993).

Equally, educational psychologists such as Benjamin Bloom (Print 1993) and Jerome Bruner (Print 1993) affected how curriculum was conceptualized and offered. Bruner’s work in the 1960’s-1980’s for example through engaged curriculum projects engaging curricula with students.

The enlargement of any curriculum is expected to involve many stakeholders. The enlargement of school curricula is an example of engagement with multiple stakeholders. Many of them repeatedly exhibit conflicting positions as Michael Apple (1993). Some of the stakeholders suggested play based learning while others structured learning.

Combo (1970) asserts that shortage of textbooks, Libraries and physical education amenities will bound the educational system from responding entirely to the new demands. In order to advance education based on excellence, better learning materials and resources are needed. Almond(1997) stressed the importance of having suitable human resources, plan and provide necessary infrastructure to sustain educational efforts.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1

Table showing the overall satisfaction level of respondents in gathering information by the teachers about the change in curriculum implementation

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Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	80	40
satisfied	60	30
Highly dissatisfied	40	20
Dissatisfied	20	10
Total	200	100

Chart 1

Chart showing the overall satisfaction level of respondents in gathering information of the teachers about the change in curriculum implementation

Interpretation:

In the above chart it is seen that 40% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the transaction of curriculum, 30% of the respondents are satisfied and 20% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and 10% of the respondents are dissatisfied with transaction of curriculum.

Table 2

Table showing the aspect of knowledge of the respondents on the background of the students who will be pioneers of this new syllabus.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	150	75
No	50	25
Total	200	100

Chart 2

Chart showing the knowledge of the respondents on the background of the students who will be pioneers of this new syllabus.

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Interpretation:

In the above chart it is understood that 75% of the respondents give importance to the background of the students while transacting curriculum and 25% of the respondents do not focus on the background of the respondents while transacting curriculum.

Table 3

Table showing how the respondents rate the knowledge on the new curriculum to be implemented.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	90	45
Very good	60	30
Good	30	15
Poor	20	10
Total	200	100

Chart 3

Chart showing how the respondents rate the knowledge on the new curriculum to be implemented.

Interpretation:

In the above chart we get to see that 45% of the respondents are rated excellent in the level of knowledge on subject matter while transacting curriculum, 30% of the respondents have very good knowledge, 15% of the respondents have good knowledge and 10% of the respondents have poor knowledge on subject matter.

Table 4

Table showing whether the respondents supported the teachers on the drafted the curriculum.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	110	55
No	90	45
Total	200	100

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Chart 4

Chart showing whether the respondents support the teachers on the drafted the curriculum.

Interpretation:

55% of the respondents support the teachers on the transacted curriculum and 45% of the respondents do not support the teachers on the transacted curriculum.

Table 5

Table showing the extent at which the respondents are valued on the suggestions and opinions provided by them while framing the curriculum

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
To a great extent	85	42.5
To a moderate extent	50	25
To a low extent	65	32.5
Total	200	100

Chart 5

Chart showing the extent at which the respondents are valued on the suggestions and opinions provided by them while framing the curriculum

Interpretation:

42.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that their suggestions are valued by the teachers to the great extent while transacting the curriculum, 25% of the respondents are of the opinion that their suggestions are valued by the teachers to a moderate extent and 32.5% of the respondents state that they are involved to a very low extent.

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Table 6

Table showing whether the respondents get support from management to implement the new curriculum.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	140	70
No	60	30
Total	200	100

Chart 6

Chart showing whether the respondents get support from management to implement the new curriculum.

Interpretation:

70% of the respondents state that they get support from the management on their views on the transacted curriculum and 30% of the respondents are of the opinion that they do not receive any support from the management while transacting curriculum.

Table 7

Table showing the issues faced by the respondents on the implementing the new curriculum.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Lack of expertise knowledge	30	15
Lack of time	65	32.5
Lack of latest technology	30	15
Lack of funds	75	37.5
Total	200	100

Chart 7

Chart showing the issues faced by the respondents on the curriculum changes

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Interpretation:

15% of the respondents state that lack of expertise knowledge is the issue on the transacted curriculum, 32.5% of the respondents state that lack of time is the major issue, 15% of the respondents state lack of latest technology is the main problem and 37.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that lack of funds is the main issue on the transacted curriculum.

Table 8

Table showing whether the respondents are provided with training while implementation of new curriculum.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	130	65
No	70	35
Total	200	100

Chart 8

Chart showing whether the respondents are provided with training for the implementation of new curriculum.

Interpretation:

65% of the respondents are of the opinion that they are provided with training facility for implementing new curriculum and 35% of the respondents are of the opinion that they are not provided with training facilities.

Table 9

Table showing the satisfaction level of the respondents on matching of the transformed curriculum with the issues of present scenario.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	70	35
Satisfied	60	30
Highly dissatisfied	40	20
Dissatisfied	30	15
Total	200	100

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Chart 9

Chart showing the satisfaction level of the respondents on matching of the transformed curriculum with the issues of present scenario.

Interpretation:

As seen in the above chart, 35% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the matching of the curriculum with the issues in the present scenario, 30% of the respondents are satisfied with the matching of curriculum according to present scenario, 20% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the matching of curriculum in accordance to the present scenario, 15% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the matching of curriculum according to the present scenario.

Table 10

Table showing the guidance of the senior teachers while implementation of curriculum by the respondents.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Always Available	75	37.5
Sometimes Available	60	30
Not Available	65	32.5
Total	200	100

Chart 10

Chart showing the guidance of senior teachers while implementation of curriculum by the respondents.

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Interpretation:

As seen above, 37.5% of the respondents state that senior teachers are always available during implementation of curriculum, 30% of the respondents state that senior teachers are sometimes available while implementation of curriculum 32.5% of the respondents state that senior teachers are not available while implementation of curriculum.

Findings

1. 40% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the gathering of information about the new curriculum, 30% of the respondents are satisfied and 20% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and 10% of the respondents are dissatisfied with gathering of information about the change in curriculum.
2. 75% of the respondents give importance to the background of the students who will be pioneers of the new curriculum.
3. 45% of the respondents are rated excellent in the level of knowledge on subject matter of the new curriculum, 30% of the respondents have very good knowledge, 15% of the respondents have good knowledge and 10% of the respondents have poor knowledge on subject matter.
4. Majority of the respondents support the teachers on the drafted curriculum.
5. 42.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that their suggestions are valued by the teachers to the great extent while framing the curriculum, 25% of the respondents are of the opinion that their suggestions are valued by the teachers to a moderate extent and 32.5% of the respondents state that they are involved to a very low extent.
6. Majority of the respondents stated that they get support from the management to implement the new curriculum as it has to match with the present trend and suit to outer world.
7. 15% of the respondents state that lack of expertise knowledge is the issue on the new curriculum, 32.5% of the respondents state that lack of time is the major issue, 15% of the respondents state lack of latest technology is the main problem and 37.5% of the respondents are of the opinion that lack of funds is the main issue on the transaction of the new curriculum.
8. 65% of the respondents are of the opinion that they are provided with training facility for implementing new curriculum and 35% of the respondents are of the opinion that they are not provided with training facilities.
9. 35% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the matching of the curriculum with the issues in the present scenario, 30% of the respondents are satisfied with the matching of curriculum according to present scenario, 20% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the matching of curriculum in accordance to the present scenario, 15% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the matching of curriculum according to the present scenario.

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10. 37.5% of the respondents state that the guidance of the senior teachers are always available during implementation of curriculum, 30% of the respondents state that the guidance are sometimes available while implementation of curriculum 32.5% of the respondents state that senior teachers are not available while implementation of curriculum.

Suggestions:

1. Management has to give due support to the teachers on implementation of new curriculum.
2. Teachers have to value the suggestions and opinions provided by their juniors on the new curriculum.
3. Teachers should be trained in the implementation of the new curriculum.
4. Management has to focus on building and equipping new technology which suits the latest curriculum.

Conclusion:

Curriculum is the base of the education system. It should be accepted by the teachers, students, parents and the community as a whole so that it focuses on developing the students to become the responsible citizens of the society. Curriculum should be adaptable to the changes and flexible so that it can be modified according to the changes of the society. For schools to be successful they should contribute to the continuous improvements in order to adapt to the changing environment. Schools should evaluate and assess regularly so that they will have knowledge on their direction.

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